

The Influence of Economic Problems, Domestic Violence, and Gambling on Divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency

Syarifah Aini¹, Syamsu Kamaruddin², Idham Irwansyah³, Najamuddin⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Postgraduate Program, Universitas Negeri Makassar, Makassar, Indonesia

ABSTRACT: The research aims to: 1) describe economic problems, domestic violence, and gambling in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. 2) Description of divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. 3) the influence of economic problems on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. 4) the influence of domestic violence on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. 5) the influence of gambling on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. 6) the influence of economic problems, domestic violence and gambling on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. The study used a descriptive quantitative approach with a population of 596 people, the number of samples was determined by the purposive sampling non-probability sampling technique using the Slovin formula and a sample of 85 respondents was obtained. Data collection techniques through google form-based questionnaires and documentation. The validity test uses Bivariate Person correlation and the reliability test is measured with Alpha Cronbach. Data analysis is in the form of descriptive and inferential statistical methods with the help of the IBM SPSS Statistics for Windows application.

The results of the study showed that: 1) economic problems, domestic violence and gambling in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency were in the "high" category respectively with an average score of variable X of 38.44 (76.87%), 35.31 (70.61%) and 34.01 (68.02%). 2) divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency is in the "high" category with an average score of 57.78 and a percentage of 77.03. 3) there is an influence of economic problems on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency, with a value of $\text{sig}.0.000 < 0.05$ and a score of $8.580 > \text{table } 1.66278$. 4) there is an influence of domestic violence on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency with a value of $\text{sig}.0.000 < 0.05$ and a score of $8.316 > \text{table } 1.66278$. 5) there is an influence of gambling on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency, where the value is $\text{sig}.0.000 < 0.05$ and the score is $4.595 > \text{Table } 1.66278$. 6) there is a simultaneous influence of economic problems, domestic violence and gambling on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency, as evidenced by the R Square value of 62%. Thus, it can be concluded that economic problems, domestic violence and gambling have an impact on the increase in divorce cases.

KEYWORDS: Economy, Domestic Violence, Gambling and Divorce

INTRODUCTION

The family institution is ideally expected to function as a safe, comfortable, and supportive environment for the growth and development of each individual within it. However, in practice, not all families are able to carry out their roles effectively. Social behavior and patterns of daily life are strongly influenced by the interactions among family members (Mogstad & Torsvik, 2023; Al-Smadi et al., 2024). The ideal functions of a family often fail to operate as intended when serious problems arise, particularly those triggered by ineffective communication and a lack of trust between spouses. Fulfilling the roles and responsibilities of husband and wife in educating and meeting the needs of the family is essential to maintaining balance within the household (Zhu et al., 2022). When either spouse neglects these responsibilities, family harmony begins to deteriorate. Consequently, when the roles and functions within the family are not carried out properly by each party, it becomes difficult to create a harmonious family environment characterized by love and affection (Sarkowi et al., 2022).

A lack of empathy, imbalance of roles, and economic pressures often trigger prolonged conflict. If these problems remain unresolved, the likelihood of divorce increases. Divorce is understood as the dissolution of the marital relationship between husband and wife, which has severe consequences for the extended family, especially children, and whose legality is determined through religious or state mechanisms (Ali et al., 2021). Generally, the main causes of the rising divorce rate include economic problems, infidelity, early marriage, parental interference, and domestic violence (Aini et al., 2025:386). These contributing factors have become central issues in efforts to maintain social stability and family harmony.

Rising living costs and increasing prices of basic goods often result in incomes that are insufficient to meet household needs. As a result, some husbands fail to fulfill their obligation to provide financial support to their wives. In 2021, economic factors became

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the second most common cause of divorce after conflict and disputes, amounting to 113,343 cases (Nadiatusholikha et al., 2024:95). This indicates that economic conditions play a decisive role in shaping the dynamics of married life. Economic hardship can give rise to further problems that worsen marital relationships.

Domestic violence is also considered a major cause of divorce, as ongoing conflict may escalate into physical and emotional harm within the household. Domestic violence is defined as acts of physical injury or abuse committed against a spouse or family member. It commonly arises from unresolved disputes between spouses or between parents and children, which ultimately lead to violent behavior (Asman, 2024).

Gambling addiction can severely disrupt marital relationships, particularly when one partner develops a compulsive behavior that is difficult to overcome. Its impact extends beyond financial instability, affecting trust, responsibility, and communication within the marriage (Ananda & Bahri, 2024:804). Such addiction often triggers financial crises, prolonged conflict, and hinders the creation of a harmonious family environment.

In recent years, the number of divorce cases in Indonesia has continued to increase. This trend is reflected at the regional level, including Bulukumba Regency in South Sulawesi. Based on preliminary observations at the Bulukumba Religious Court, there were 1,531 divorce cases recorded between 2023 and 2024. Of these, 242 were *cerai talak* (husband-initiated divorce), while 1,289 were *cerai gugat* (wife-initiated divorce). The highest number of cases was reported in Gantarang District, one of ten districts in Bulukumba Regency, with 298 cases recorded between 2023 and 2024 (43 *cerai talak* and 255 *cerai gugat*). According to the 2019 data from the Bulukumba Statistics Bureau, Gantarang District has the highest population in the regency, with approximately 75,980 residents.

A study by Zakih (2024), titled “The Influence of Economic Factors in Divorce Cases on Religious Court Decisions in Jember (Case Study of PA Jember Decision No. 4318/Pdt.G/2023/PA.Jr)” shows a significant relationship between economic conditions and court decisions, indicated by a very low p-value in the Chi-Square test ($p = 0.0015$). Unstable economic conditions such as low income and high debt burdens play a role in influencing decisions related to alimony and child custody.

Divorce caused by domestic violence often results in long-term trauma rooted in unresolved conflicts and misunderstandings. Research by Darmawan (2024:407), titled “The Influence of Divorce Rates in Java Island Due to Domestic Violence,” found that the four highest contributing factors to divorce in Java are conflict and disputes, economic problems, spousal death, and domestic violence. Domestic violence significantly contributes to the high number of divorce cases on the island.

Another noteworthy contributing factor to divorce is the involvement of one spouse in gambling activities. A study by Utami et al. (2025:14), titled “Online Gambling: A Trigger for Divorce in Modern Families,” revealed that online gambling addiction significantly contributes to financial instability, emotional detachment, recurring conflict, and the deterioration of communication and trust in marital relationships. Many respondents reported feelings of betrayal, frustration, and exhaustion due to their partner’s uncontrollable gambling behavior.

Preliminary observations also indicate that economic pressures, domestic violence, and gambling habits have increasingly become underlying sources of conflict and declining trust within households. According to the Head of Islamic Community Guidance at the Office of the Ministry of Religious Affairs in Bulukumba Regency, the high divorce rate in Gantarang District during 2023–2024 was predominantly caused by gambling, alcohol abuse, domestic violence, and economic problems. Based on these considerations, the researcher finds it necessary to conduct a study entitled “The Influence of Economic Problems, Domestic Violence, and Gambling on Divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency.”

RESEARCH METHOD

This study employs a quantitative research method using questionnaire-based data collection and descriptive statistical analysis. The research variables consist of economic problems (X1), domestic violence (X2), and gambling (X3) as the independent variables, while divorce (Y) serves as the dependent variable.

The population of this study includes all divorced couples from 2023 to 2024 in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. Based on calculations using the Slovin formula, with a total population of 596 individuals, the required sample size is 85 respondents. The study utilizes a non-probability sampling technique, specifically purposive sampling. The research was conducted from September to October 2025 using an online questionnaire.

The questionnaire consists of 45 items, including respondent profiles and indicators of the research variables. All questionnaire items were measured using a Likert scale ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). Data analysis was conducted using descriptive and inferential statistical techniques to test hypotheses and examine the relationships between the independent variables (X) and the dependent variable (Y), using IBM SPSS Statistics version 25 for Windows.

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RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Marriage is a union that requires not only a single aspect to function effectively, but rather a combination of emotional, social, and economic dimensions. Maintaining a balance between physical and emotional needs within a family is crucial, particularly for married couples. When one of these essential household needs such as economic stability is not fulfilled, imbalances may arise in the performance of family roles and functions. This imbalance can escalate into conflict, which may lead to physical violence or even the adoption of harmful coping mechanisms such as gambling. Such conditions ultimately weaken the bond between spouses or other family members.

The findings of this study conducted in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency, based on descriptive statistical analysis, indicate that the economic problems variable (X1) has a mean score of 38.44 with an overall response percentage of 76.87%. The domestic violence variable (X2) obtained a mean score of 35.31 and a response percentage of 70.61%. The gambling variable (X3) recorded a mean score of 34.01 with a percentage of 68.02%. Meanwhile, the divorce variable (Y) yielded a mean score of 57.78 with a response percentage of 77.03%. Overall, all variables fall within the high category.

Hypothesis testing was conducted using the t-test and multiple linear regression analysis. The t-test is used to determine the partial influence of each independent variable (X) on the dependent variable (Y). Multiple linear regression analysis, on the other hand, examines the collective influence of all independent variables on divorce. The detailed results of the hypothesis testing are presented in the table below:

Table 1. t Test

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	58.835	.476		125.610	.000
	Economic Problem (X1)	.101	.012	.664	8.580	.000
	Domestic Violence (X2)	.101	.012	.679	8.316	.000
	Gambling (X3)	.051	.011	.373	4.595	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Divorce

Based on the analysis, it was found that if the value of $t_{hitung} > t_{tabel}$, then there is an influence of the independent variables (X) on the dependent variable (Y). The significance values for variables X1, X2, and X3 were all 0.000, which is lower than 0.05. Using the t-table value of 1.66278, the results of the t-test show that: for variable X1, $t_{hitung} (8.580) > t_{tabel} (1.66278)$; for variable X2, $t_{hitung} (8.316) > t_{tabel} (1.66278)$; and for variable X3, $t_{hitung} (4.595) > t_{tabel} (1.66278)$. These results indicate that all independent variables economic problems, domestic violence, and gambling have a positive and significant effect on divorce.

To determine whether the variables economic problems (X1), domestic violence (X2), and gambling (X3) simultaneously influence divorce (Y), a multiple linear regression analysis (F-test) was conducted through SPSS Statistics using the ANOVA table presented below:

Tabel 2. Multiple Regression Analysis

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	112.905	3	37.635	44.052	.000^b
	Residual	69.201	81	.854		
	Total	182.106	84			

Dependent Variable: Divorce (Y)

b. Predictors: (constant), Gambling (X3), Domestic Violence (X2) and Economic Problems (X1)

In this case, the F-table value is 3.11. Based on the results of the F-test, it is shown that the significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and the calculated F value of $44.052 > 3.11$. Therefore, it can be understood that all independent variables (X) simultaneously have a significant effect on the dependent variable (Y).

Furthermore, to determine the percentage of the combined influence of the independent variables (X) on the dependent variable (Y), a coefficient of determination test was conducted using the Model Summary output, specifically by examining the R-square value in the table presented below:

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Tabel 3. Coefficients Determinant

Model Summary				
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.787 ^a	.620	.606	.924
a. Predictors: (Constant), Gambling (X3), Domestic Violence (X2) and Economic Problems (X1)				

Based on these results, the R-square value is 0.620, which indicates that the three independent variables (X) simultaneously influence divorce by 62%, while the remaining 38% is affected by other factors outside the scope of this study and not explained in this research.

As one of the many factors contributing to marital dissolution, economic problems have been shown to play a significant role, as reflected in the findings of this study. This is consistent with the research conducted by Hakim (2021), titled “*Analysis of the Influence of Economic Factors on Divorce Rates in Berau Regency*,” which found that economic factors significantly affect divorce rates. This conclusion is supported by the t-test results, where $t_{hitung} < t_{tabel}$ or $-3.549 < -2.101$, and the significance value is lower than the probability threshold ($0.002 < 0.05$). Based on these findings, it is evident that economic problems exert a positive and significant influence on divorce. Thus, an increase in economic hardship is likely to heighten divorce rates, posing substantial challenges to both families and society at large. Economic problems in this context are often linked to difficulties in fulfilling basic household needs over time.

Domestic violence has also been shown to contribute to the rising number of divorce cases within communities, particularly within families. This assertion is reinforced by the study of Bo and Yating (2023), titled “*Long-Term Impact of Domestic Violence on Individuals: An Empirical Study Based on Education, Health, and Life Satisfaction*,” which found that domestic violence significantly reduces educational achievement. Among the four forms of violence examined, emotional abuse had the most severe negative impact on educational outcomes compared with physical violence, neglect, and witnessing violence. Domestic violence also reduces victims’ health status and life satisfaction while increasing the risk of mental health problems. These findings illustrate the extensive negative consequences of domestic violence on victims. Given these impacts, many victims choose to leave their marriages rather than endure long-term trauma. The study provides strong evidence that as domestic violence increases, divorce rates also rise, especially considering the physical, psychological, and social consequences experienced by victims.

Gambling behavior within families has become a persistent threat to marital stability and overall family well-being. Research by Suraiya et al. (2024), titled “*Family Disharmony Due to Online Gambling in Sidoarjo Regency: A Qur’anic Family Systems Perspective*,” found that online gambling has a significant impact on family harmony and welfare. In Sidoarjo Regency, online gambling has emerged as a major contributor to economic instability and disruptions in household relationships. The resulting forms of family disharmony were classified into three categories: (1) mild disharmony, characterized by conflicts between husband and wife; (2) moderate disharmony, involving disputes between spouses that extend to other family members; and (3) severe disharmony, marked by the submission of divorce petitions to the Religious Court. Gambling behavior often leads to financial instability and the erosion of trust between partners. Persistent tension can escalate into disputes and domestic violence. Consequently, divorce frequently becomes the final option to end such ongoing conflict.

The theoretical foundation of this study is based on conflict theory. According to Karl Marx, conflict theory emphasizes that society consists of groups with competing interests, wherein economic inequality serves as the primary source of conflict (Setiadi & Kolip, 2015:365; Brisset et al., 2022). Furthermore, conflict arises because society is continuously undergoing change, accompanied by persistent contradictions among its elements (Ritzer, 1992:30; Kühne et al., 2023). Within the family, differences in roles and status may trigger disputes among members. Divorce can be viewed as a manifestation of conflict resulting from imbalances within family structures. Economic problems, domestic violence, and gambling intensify power disparities and create inequities within marital relationships. Economic difficulties often lead to unequal distributions of resources between household income and expenditure, generating disputes between spouses. Domestic violence represents a conflict centered on power and domination, where one partner attempts to control the other through coercion and abuse. Gambling, likewise, fosters conflict due to competing financial interests between partners. Its detrimental effects especially material losses further deteriorate household financial conditions and exacerbate marital instability.

CONCLUSIONS

The Towani Tolotang community in Parepare City generally holds a perception that formal schooling is not yet a primary priority. Many members of the community place greater emphasis on customary values and religious beliefs as the foundation for shaping children’s character and intelligence. Traditional education is often viewed as equivalent to, or even more important than, formal

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education. Several factors contribute to school dropout among Towani Tolotang children in Parepare City, namely limited interest or motivation toward schooling, economic constraints, parents' low level of education; and sociocultural conditions, which include neighborhood influences and early marriage. The impacts of school dropout within the Towani Tolotang community in Parepare City include reduced employment opportunities, feelings of inferiority or low self-confidence, limited skills and knowledge; and the need for children to support their family's economic conditions.

Parents, as the child's first educators, are expected to provide strong moral support and sustained motivation to encourage their children to continue formal schooling. They should also pay closer attention to the continuity of their children's educational journey. A shift in mindset is needed so that education is viewed as a fundamental necessity, equipping children with the knowledge and skills required to face future challenges. Traditional leaders within the Towani Tolotang community in Parepare City are encouraged to take an active role in promoting the importance of formal education. As influential figures who shape community values and behavior, they hold a strategic position in guiding public perceptions. It is hoped that traditional leaders can help cultivate a collective awareness that formal education is a basic right for every child and an essential component of personal and social development and the government is expected to provide more serious and targeted attention to educational issues within the Towani Tolotang community in Parepare City. Continuous efforts are needed to prevent school dropout, including regular monitoring and mentoring of school-aged children. Strong collaboration among traditional leaders, government institutions, and parents is essential to address the multiple factors contributing to dropout. Such coordinated efforts will help ensure that no future generation within the Towani Tolotang community is hindered in accessing proper education.

The description of economic problems, domestic violence, and gambling in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency shows that all three variables fall into the "high" category. The average score for the economic problems variable is 38.44, with a percentage level of 76.87%. For the domestic violence variable, the mean score is 35.31 with a percentage level of 70.61%. Meanwhile, the gambling variable has a mean score of 34.01 with a percentage level of 68.02%. The description of divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency also falls into the "high" category, with an average score of 57.78 and a percentage level of 77.03%.

There is an influence of economic problems on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. This statement is supported by a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a calculated t-value of $8.580 > t$ -table value of 1.66278, indicating that economic problems significantly affect divorce. There is an influence of domestic violence on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. This is evidenced by a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a calculated t-value of $8.316 > t$ -table value of 1.66278, demonstrating that domestic violence significantly affects divorce. There is an influence of gambling on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. This is shown by a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a calculated t-value of $4.595 > t$ -table value of 1.66278, indicating that gambling significantly affects divorce. There is a simultaneous (combined) influence of economic problems, domestic violence, and gambling on divorce in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. This is confirmed through the F-test, which shows a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ and a calculated F-value of $44.052 > 3.11$. The R-square value of 0.620 indicates that the three independent variables economic problems, domestic violence, and gambling jointly influence divorce by 62%, while the remaining 38% is affected by factors outside the scope of this study. Overall, economic problems, domestic violence, and gambling contribute to the increasing rate of divorce.

This study is expected to provide theoretical contributions by demonstrating that economic problems, domestic violence, and gambling significantly influence the rise in divorce, particularly in Gantarang District, Bulukumba Regency. This implies the need for comprehensive efforts from families (both spouses), the community, the government, and relevant institutions to reduce divorce rates by addressing economic issues, preventing domestic violence, and minimizing gambling practices that have the potential to trigger marital dissolution.

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